

Dehydration and rehydration effects on natural tooth color

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to evaluate time-dependent changes in the color characteristics of intact maxillary anterior teeth during controlled dehydration and subsequent natural rehydration using spectrophotometric analysis. Thirty systemically healthy subjects aged 18–30 years with intact maxillary anterior teeth were included. Tooth color was measured using a spectrophotometer at baseline, during a 30-min dehydration phase, and during a 30-min passive rehydration phase. Color differences (ΔE) relative to baseline were calculated, and changes in L^* , a^* , and b^* coordinates in the CIELAB system were analyzed. Dehydration resulted in a progressive increase in ΔE , reaching a maximum of 3.00 ± 1.62 at 30 min, accompanied by increased lightness and reduced chromaticity. During rehydration, ΔE values decreased steadily, approaching baseline levels by 60 min. The results demonstrate that tooth dehydration induces perceptible but largely reversible color changes, highlighting the importance of hydration control during clinical shade selection.

Keywords

color change, dehydration, rehydration, spectrophotometry, tooth color

Introduction

Shade selection remains one of the most critical and challenging aspects of esthetic dental treatment. The perceived color of natural teeth is the result of complex interactions between incident light, enamel translucency, dentin chroma, and the optical properties of the surrounding oral environment. Even subtle alterations in these factors may lead to perceptible differences in tooth color, affecting both patient satisfaction and restorative outcomes (Mohammed et al. 2022).

Clinical procedures such as isolation, prolonged mouth opening, air-drying, and restorative manipulation frequently induce partial or complete dehydration of enam-

el surfaces (Liondev et al. 2025). Dehydration alters the refractive index mismatch between enamel prisms and interprismatic spaces, increasing light scattering and resulting in higher lightness and reduced chroma. These transient changes may lead to erroneous shade selection, particularly during restorative and prosthetic procedures (Hatırlı et al. 2021).

Previous studies have demonstrated that dehydration can produce perceptible color changes; however, reported methodologies vary widely in dehydration protocols, measurement timing, and analytical approaches. Moreover, limited data exist regarding the time course of dehydration-induced color changes and subsequent spontaneous rehydration under physiological conditions (Suliman et al.

2019; Alamé and Mehanna Zogheib 2023). Recent studies have further demonstrated that dehydration-related color changes may vary according to age and tooth developmental status (Sharmila et al. 2022; Buldur et al. 2024).

Tooth color is not a static property but a dynamic optical phenomenon influenced by both intrinsic tissue characteristics and extrinsic environmental factors. Among these, the presence of water within enamel and dentin plays a critical role in overall color perception, determining translucency and light scattering. The refractive index of water closely approximates that of hydroxyapatite; therefore, water loss from interprismatic spaces leads to increased refractive mismatch, enhanced light scattering, and altered chromatic expression of dental tissues (ten Bosch and Coops 1995).

During routine dental procedures, temporary dehydration is frequently induced by prolonged mouth opening, isolation, air-drying, or continuous suction. These conditions may produce transient yet clinically relevant changes in tooth color, particularly in the esthetic zone. Despite the widespread clinical relevance of this phenomenon, limited data exist regarding the time-dependent behavior of dehydration-induced color changes and the extent to which natural rehydration restores baseline optical characteristics. A clearer understanding of these dynamics is essential for optimizing clinical protocols for shade selection and improving the predictability of esthetic outcomes (Ruiz-López et al. 2021).

The aim of the present study was to evaluate time-dependent changes in the color of intact maxillary anterior teeth during controlled dehydration and subsequent passive rehydration under physiological conditions.

Materials and methods

Study design and participants

This clinical observational study included 30 systemically healthy volunteers (15 males and 15 females) aged 18–30 years. All participants presented intact natural dentition in the maxillary anterior region. The maxillary anterior teeth included in the study were analyzed individually.

Participants were selected following a comprehensive clinical examination assessing dental hard tissues, periodontal status, and oral hygiene. Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects prior to participation.

Inclusion criteria

- Age 18–30 years;
- Good general health;
- Intact maxillary anterior teeth (13, 12, 11, 21, 22, and 23);
- Absence of carious lesions;
- No restorations, crowns, veneers, or prosthetic restorations;
- No signs of gingivitis or periodontitis;

- Absence of orthodontic anomalies or tooth rotation;
- Good oral hygiene without plaque or calculus;
- Professional scaling performed one week prior to measurements;
- Non-smokers;
- No history of home or in-office bleaching within the previous 6 months.

Exclusion criteria

- Caries, restorations, or prosthetic appliances on study teeth;
- Periodontal inflammation;
- Current or previous orthodontic treatment;
- Presence of plaque or calculus;
- Smoking;
- Systemic diseases or medications affecting salivary flow or mineral balance.

Measurement conditions

All measurements were performed under standardized clinical conditions in the same treatment room by the same operator. The room lighting consisted of a combination of natural daylight and consistent artificial illumination. The dental unit reflector was switched off to avoid additional light interference.

Participants were positioned in a semi-reclined position at approximately 45°, which was maintained throughout all measurement intervals.

Prior to baseline measurements, tooth surfaces were cleaned using a soft brush and distilled water, without toothpaste or abrasive agents.

Tooth color measurement protocol

Tooth color was measured using the SpectroShade spectrophotometer, which records color coordinates in the CIELAB color space (L^* , a^* , b^*). Before each measurement session, the device underwent mandatory two-point calibration according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Measurements were performed on the vestibular surfaces of teeth 13, 12, 11, 21, 22, and 23. The device was positioned perpendicular to the tooth surface, ensuring that the measurement field covered the central vestibular area without including gingival tissues. Correct positioning was verified using the device's visual indicator, and measurements were recorded only under optimal conditions.

The dominant tooth color was recorded without dividing the crown into anatomical thirds to ensure high repeatability during successive short-interval measurements.

Dehydration and rehydration protocol

Baseline measurements were recorded immediately after cleaning and prior to dehydration (0 min) (Fig. 1).

Dehydration was induced using a cheek retractor and continuous active suction in the sublingual area to prevent

Figure 1. Clinical appearance of the maxillary anterior teeth at baseline before dehydration.

salivary contact. Participants were instructed to keep their mouths open and breathe orally throughout the dehydration phase. Measurements were performed at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 min.

Immediately after the 30-min dehydration measurement, the cheek retractor was removed, and suction was discontinued. Passive rehydration then proceeded under physiological oral conditions without fluid intake. Measurements were subsequently recorded at 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, and 60 min (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Clinical appearance of the maxillary anterior teeth after 30 min of controlled dehydration.

Color difference calculation and statistical analysis

Color differences (ΔE) relative to baseline were calculated using the CIE76 formula based on changes in L^* , a^* , and b^* values.

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics. Repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni *post hoc* correction was applied. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Color changes during dehydration (0–30 min)

A progressive increase in mean ΔE values was observed during dehydration. From a baseline value of $\Delta E = 0$, a

noticeable increase occurred as early as 5 min (0.74 ± 0.21), continuing at 10 min (1.46 ± 0.45), 15 min (2.11 ± 0.72), 20 min (2.55 ± 1.06), and 25 min (2.86 ± 1.36). The maximum mean ΔE was recorded at 30 min (3.00 ± 1.62) (Fig. 3; Table 1).

Figure 3. Dynamic changes in ΔE during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of ΔE values during the dehydration phase (0–30 min).

	0'	5'	10'	15'	20'	25'	30'
MEAN	0	0.74	1.46	2.11	2.55	2.86	3
SD	0	0.21	0.45	0.72	1.06	1.36	1.62
MIN	0	0.17	0.24	0.35	0.39	0.41	0.12
MAX	0	1.28	2.6	3.74	4.64	5.25	5.65

Repeated-measures ANOVA demonstrated a statistically significant effect of time ($p < 0.001$). *Post hoc* analysis revealed significant differences between baseline and all subsequent time points. No significant difference was found between 20 and 25 min ($p = 0.183$), suggesting a temporary deceleration in the rate of change.

Color changes during rehydration (30–60 min)

During rehydration, ΔE values decreased progressively from 3.00 ± 1.62 at 30 min to 0.14 ± 0.12 at 60 min. Significant differences were observed between all consecutive time points ($p < 0.001$), indicating continuous recovery of baseline color (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of ΔE values during the rehydration phase (30–60 min).

	30'	35'	40'	45'	50'	55'	60'
MEAN	3	2.11	1.43	0.78	0.39	0.2	0.14
SD	1.62	1.09	0.63	0.33	0.14	0.08	0.12
MIN	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.1	0.1	0.06	0
MAX	5.65	4.18	2.73	1.63	0.89	0.52	0.39

Changes in CIELAB coordinates

Lightness (L^*) increased steadily during dehydration, reaching a peak at 30 min (74.72 ± 1.88), followed by gradual reduction during rehydration to baseline levels at 60 min (Fig. 4; Table 3).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of L^* during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

	0'	5'	10'	15'	20'	25'	30'	35'	40'	45'	50'	55'	60'
Mean	72.43	72.95	73.51	74.03	74.42	74.65	74.72	73.84	73.19	72.74	72.52	72.44	72.43
SD	1.95	1.95	2	2	1.94	1.92	1.88	1.8	1.82	1.88	1.92	1.92	1.93
Min	68.2	68.9	69.2	69.3	70	70.3	70.4	70.4	69.6	69.1	68.7	68.5	68.4
MAX	77.8	77.9	78	78.1	78.2	78.2	78.3	78.1	78	77.9	77.8	77.8	77.8

Figure 4. Dynamic changes in L^* during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

Red–green coordinate (a^*) decreased during dehydration, reflecting reduced red chroma, and recovered progressively during rehydration (Fig. 5; Table 4).

Figure 5. Dynamic changes in a^* during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

Yellow–blue coordinate (b^*) exhibited a pronounced reduction during dehydration, indicating loss of yellowness, and demonstrated near-complete recovery during rehydration (Fig. 6; Table 5).

Figure 6. Dynamic changes in b^* during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

Discussion

The present study demonstrated that tooth dehydration induces statistically significant and clinically perceptible color changes in maxillary anterior teeth. A progressive increase in ΔE values was observed during dehydration, accompanied predominantly by increased lightness (L^*) and reduced chromaticity. These findings confirm that even short-term moisture loss can substantially alter the optical properties of dental tissues (Haciali et al. 2025).

The observed increase in lightness during dehydration is likely related to enhanced light scattering caused by water loss from interprismatic enamel spaces, resulting in reduced translucency and altered chromatic expression of dental tissues (Vaarkamp et al. 1995). Concurrent reductions in a^* and b^* values indicate diminished red and yellow chromatic components, contributing to the characteristic brighter appearance of dehydrated teeth (Ruiz-López et al. 2021).

The simultaneous reduction in the b^* coordinate indicates a decrease in the yellowness of tooth color, fur-

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of a^* during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

	0'	5'	10'	15'	20'	25'	30'	35'	40'	45'	50'	55'	60'
MEAN	1.54	1.32	1.14	0.96	0.79	0.67	0.63	0.92	1.14	1.34	1.44	1.51	1.52
SD	0.5	0.49	0.51	0.5	0.51	0.52	0.52	0.46	0.45	0.46	0.48	0.49	0.49
MIN	0	0	0	0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
MAX	2.5	2.2	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.1	2	2	2	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.4

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of b^* during tooth dehydration and rehydration.

	0'	5'	10'	15'	20'	25'	30'	35'	40'	45'	50'	55'	60'
MEAN	14.03	13.51	12.9	12.3	11.74	11.31	11.1	11.86	12.58	13.18	13.59	13.82	13.96
SD	1.11	1.09	1.2	1.34	1.42	1.49	1.6	1.3	1.12	1.07	1.07	1.09	1.11
MIN	8.8	8.6	8.4	8.3	8.2	8	7.9	8.1	8.3	8.5	8.6	8.7	8.8
MAX	15.8	15.2	15.6	15.8	15.3	14.9	14.6	14.4	14.5	15	15.3	15.5	15.6

ther contributing to the overall increase in ΔE . Although changes in the a^* coordinate were less pronounced, their consistent pattern highlights the multifactorial nature of dehydration-induced color shifts. Similar *in vitro* findings were reported by Du et al., who observed statistically significant increases in L^* values after prolonged dehydration of extracted maxillary central incisors, confirming that dehydration predominantly causes teeth to appear lighter even in the absence of intraoral physiological factors (Du et al. 2012). The plateau observed during the later stages of dehydration may suggest partial saturation of dehydration effects, possibly reflecting equilibrium between surface evaporation and residual intrinsic moisture (Alamé and Mehanna Zogheib 2023).

The magnitude of ΔE values observed during dehydration exceeded commonly accepted perceptibility thresholds, underscoring the risk of clinically relevant shade mismatch if hydration status is ignored (Pecho et al. 2016). These findings are consistent with Burki et al., who demonstrated significant dehydration-induced changes in all CIELAB coordinates during 30 min of rubber dam isolation. Similar to the present study, dehydrated teeth exhibited increased lightness and clinically perceptible color alterations confirmed by both instrumental and visual assessment. However, Burki et al. reported incomplete recovery of baseline color after 30 min of rehydration, whereas near-complete reversal of ΔE values was observed in the present study (Burki et al. 2013). These differences may be associated with variations in dehydration protocols, hydration conditions, and measurement techniques.

Similar results were reported by Hatırlı et al., who observed clinically significant dehydration-induced color changes after 30 min, with many teeth exceeding perceptibility and acceptability thresholds. Although their study demonstrated more prolonged recovery during rehydration, both investigations emphasize the substantial clinical influence of dehydration on shade selection procedures (Hatırlı et al. 2021).

Additional studies further support the present findings. Ahmed et al. demonstrated that prolonged dehydration significantly affects spectrophotometric tooth color measurements, with progressive increases in color differences and lightness values over time (Ahmed et al. 2022). Similarly, Du et al. observed significant increases in L^* values after dehydration of extracted maxillary central incisors, confirming that dehydration predominantly causes teeth to appear lighter even in the absence of intraoral physiological factors.

Comparable clinically relevant findings have also been reported in studies evaluating dehydration caused by routine dental procedures, including prolonged mouth opening and impression-taking. Significant increases in L^* values and clinically perceptible color changes persisting for up to 30 min were observed, highlighting the potential influence of common clinical procedures on shade-matching accuracy (Eroglu et al. 2023).

Interestingly, the plateau observed between 20 and 25 min in the present study may suggest partial saturation of dehydration effects, possibly reflecting equilibrium between surface evaporation and residual intrinsic moisture. During rehydration, ΔE values progressively decreased, approaching baseline levels within 30 min under physiological conditions. From a clinical perspective, these findings reinforce the importance of performing shade selection prior to prolonged isolation or restorative procedures involving continuous suction and mouth opening (Tabatabaian et al. 2021).

Several limitations of the present study should be acknowledged. First, the study population consisted exclusively of young, systemically healthy individuals with intact maxillary anterior teeth. Although this homogeneity reduced confounding variables and enhanced internal validity, it may limit the generalizability of the findings to older populations, teeth with restorations, or patients with altered enamel structure or salivary flow (Demirel and Tuncdemir 2019). This limitation is further supported by another study showing that dehydration- and rehydration-induced color and whiteness changes vary significantly among different age groups, with older individuals exhibiting less pronounced optical alterations compared with younger participants (Sharmila et al. 2022). Similarly, Buldur et al. demonstrated that immature permanent teeth exhibit rapid and clinically perceptible color changes during the early stages of dehydration, suggesting that tooth developmental status may also influence dehydration-related optical behavior (Buldur et al. 2024).

Second, dehydration was induced under controlled clinical conditions that may not fully replicate the variability of dehydration encountered during routine dental procedures. Factors such as airflow intensity, ambient humidity, and duration of isolation may influence the magnitude of color changes in real clinical settings (Bannister et al. 2023).

Third, only passive natural rehydration was evaluated. Active rehydration methods, such as water rinsing or saliva substitutes, were not evaluated and may influence the rate and extent of color recovery (Suliman et al. 2019).

Finally, while spectrophotometric measurements provide objective and highly reproducible data, this study was limited to instrumental color assessment and did not address visual color perception by clinicians or patients. Future research combining instrumental analysis with visual assessment may improve the clinical applicability of these findings (Liberato et al. 2019).

Conclusion

Controlled dehydration of maxillary anterior teeth resulted in time-dependent color changes, characterized mainly by increased lightness and reduced chromaticity. These changes were largely reversible following natural rehydration within 30 min.

The highest color deviation was recorded at the end of the dehydration period, whereas the subsequent progressive reduction in ΔE values during rehydration confirmed the transient nature of these changes.

Within the limitations of this study, the clinical implication is that shade selection should ideally be performed before dehydration of the dental tissues. Otherwise, it should be postponed until physiological rehydration has occurred to minimize the risk of esthetic discrepancies.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
